

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Different 2-Pyrazolin-5-One Mannich Bases

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Manuscript received 12 August 1980, revised 8 January 1981, accepted 18 April 1981

2-Pyrazolin-5-one derivatives undergo Mannich base type of condensation. Fungitoxicity of thirty-two Mannich bases were studied against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.) and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Some compounds were found to be active.

ON the basis of the significant fungicidal activity of 2-pyrazolin-5-one of our earlier work¹⁻⁵, the present investigation was extended to synthesize their Mannich bases and to study their fungitoxicity. Further the Mannich base condensation of 1-(*p*-NO₂ phenyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one reported earlier⁶, prompted us to investigate the series of Mannich base reaction of 2-pyrazolin-5-one.

2-Pyrazolin-5-one derivatives undergo Mannich base type of reaction with formaldehyde and substituted aryl amines to yield 4-N-(aryl)-amino methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives. The structure of Mannich base was established from the analytical values and from ir data.

Fig. A

The keto-enol tautomeric form of pyrazolone nucleus was established from its absorption spectra which exhibits a characteristic carbonyl group absorption band at 1690 cm⁻¹ and also an enolic broad band in between 2850-2700 cm⁻¹. Band at 1600 cm⁻¹ and 3110 cm⁻¹ ascribed for the heterocyclic ring and for the N-H stretching vibration respectively.

Thirty-two Mannich bases thus prepared have been screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.) and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*, by the standard procedure⁷ using spore germination method at various concentrations. The fungicidal activities of the thirty-two compounds at 1000 ppm concentration are given in Table 1.

It was found that the compounds Sl. No. 5, 17 and 18 were active against both the pathogens and Sl. No. 30 is only active against the pathogen *P. oryzae*. Sl. No. 19, 25 and 28 were active against the pathogen *H. oryzae*. It was observed that

TABLE-1

Sl. No. 1-16 (R₁=Ph)

Sl. No. 17-32 (R₁=H)

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₂	m.p. °C	% of C Found (Calcd.)	% of H Found (Calcd.)	% of N Found (Calcd.)	% of germination of inhibition at 1000 ppm	
						<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	149	73.08 (73.11)	5.90 (6.003)	14.68 (15.08)	34.6	37.9
2.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	140	64.98 (65.17)	5.05 (5.11)	12.95 (13.41)	20.5	38.6
3.	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	199	64.85 (65.17)	5.02 (5.11)	12.81 (13.41)	25.5	19.5
4.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	145	64.64 (65.17)	5.03 (5.11)	12.69 (13.41)	21.4	43.5
5.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	159	73.19 (73.72)	6.11 (6.48)	13.83 (14.33)	66.6	79.9
6.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	195	73.28 (73.72)	6.20 (6.48)	13.95 (14.83)	14	19.5

(Table 1 Contd.)

7.	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	79.09 (73.72)	6.12 (6.48)	14.01 (14.33)	29.5	21.5
8.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	119	62.55 (62.96)	4.21 (4.93)	17.19 (17.28)	32.5	66.8
9.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	84	62.34 (62.96)	3.99 (4.93)	17.06 (17.28)	24.7	32.0
10.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	120	62.26 (62.96)	3.97 (4.93)	17.11 (17.28)	34.5	34.0
11.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	172	68.99 (69.67)	5.91 (6.45)	12.78 (13.54)	28.5	47.7
12.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	151	68.87 (69.67)	5.91 (6.45)	12.78 (13.54)	22.2	29.0
13.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	181	68.69 (69.67)	5.89 (6.45)	12.98 (13.54)	20.5	24.0
14.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	133	69.85 (70.33)	6.22 (6.76)	11.99 (12.96)	22.5	36.5
15.	α -Naphthyl	215	72.92 (73.55)	5.15 (5.74)	12.21 (12.73)	21.5	33.5
16.	β -Naphthyl	205	73.01 (73.55)	5.97 (5.74)	12.42 (12.73)	24.5	36.5
17.	C ₆ H ₆	155	64.86 (65.02)	5.97 (6.40)	19.89 (20.68)	72.3	64.5
18.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	162	54.84 (55.69)	4.79 (5.06)	17.24 (17.68)	60.09	56.5
19.	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	300	54.76 (55.69)	4.88 (5.06)	17.13 (17.68)	28.7	62.6
20.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	171	54.02 (55.69)	4.67 (5.06)	17.26 (17.68)	32.6	34.6
21.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	187	65.96 (66.35)	5.79 (6.35)	18.77 (19.35)	22.5	30.7
22.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	235d	65.87 (66.35)	5.76 (6.35)	18.49 (19.35)	30.5	36.6
23.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	156	65.99 (66.35)	5.89 (6.35)	18.91 (19.35)	29.2	38.6
24.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	200	52.65 (53.22)	4.09 (4.83)	21.81 (22.66)	31.4	25
25.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	175	52.64 (53.22)	4.26 (4.83)	21.97 (22.66)	24.5	74.5
26.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	248	52.81 (53.22)	4.10 (4.83)	22.12 (22.66)	30.5	28.6
27.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	219	60.98 (61.80)	6.25 (6.48)	17.67 (18.02)	35.6	49.8
28.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	251	60.89 (61.80)	6.19 (6.48)	17.29 (18.02)	40.8	51.8
29.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	260	60.95 (61.80)	6.20 (6.48)	17.56 (18.02)	21.5	26.5
30.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	215	62.76 (63.59)	6.01 (6.08)	17.02 (17.14)	63.4	36.5
31.	α -Naphthyl	302	70.76 (71.14)	5.27 (5.92)	16.14 (16.60)	28.5	26.7
32.	β -Naphthyl	305	70.82 (71.14)	5.11 (5.92)	16.15 (16.60)	28.6	40.8

Sl. No. 5 was the most active against the pathogen *H. oryzae* which exhibits 52, 62 and 79% at 400, 800 and 1000 ppm concentration respectively.

Experimental

All the m.p.s are uncorrected. The ir in nujol was recorded in Perkin-Elmer Limited, Beaconsfield, Bucks IR Spectrophotometer.

Procedure for the preparation of 4-N-(aryl)-amino methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one: A mixture of 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives (0.01M), 37% of formaldehyde (0.02M), arylamine (0.012M), 20% HCl (2 ml) and ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 4 hrs and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight. It was then concentrated. On cooling the solid mass thus obtained was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The compound is soluble in aq. NaOH and gives red colouration with FeCl₃.

Acknowledgement

We thank ICAR, New Delhi for financial support and C.R.R.I., Cuttack for providing facilities to carry out the fungicidal tests.

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